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The Global General Infrastructure Index

It grew by an average of 3.67% between 2013 and 2022

The General Infrastructure Index evaluates the general infrastructure at the country level in terms of how it promotes innovation. It considers various aspects such as access to information and communication technologies (ICT), measuring the availability and use of the internet and broadband. Additionally, it evaluates the effective use of ICT by the population and businesses. The quality of online services provided by the government is also an evaluation element. The quality of general infrastructure, including transportation infrastructure like roads, railways, ports, and airports, and energy infrastructure like power grids and other physical infrastructures that support economic and social activities, is another key aspect. Finally, the country's commitment to sustainable practices, such as renewable energy consumption, waste management, and pollution reduction, is examined. In summary, General Infrastructure is a crucial tool for understanding how favorable a country's infrastructure is to innovation, an essential element for economic and technological development. The data are available between 2013 and 2022.

The Global General Infrastructure Index in 2022. Analyzing the data related to the "General Infrastructure" indicator of the Global Innovation Index 2022, there is a significant disparity among countries, highlighting how general infrastructure is a crucial element for development and innovation. At the top of the rankings is Qatar with a score of 76.2, followed by Norway (72.5) and Sweden (68.3). These countries, known for their advanced economies and the quality of their infrastructure, demonstrate a significant commitment to innovation through the construction of solid infrastructural foundations. The UAE and Canada share the fourth position with a score of 64.6, followed by Bahrain (64.3), Iceland (61.8), and Finland (61.2). These countries, although diverse in terms of economy size and structure, show a common commitment to improving their infrastructure to support innovation. Extensive use of ICT, along with high-quality transportation and energy infrastructure, contributes to these high scores. South Korea and the US, with scores of 58.7 and 58.6 respectively, reflect the importance of advanced technological infrastructure in their highly industrialized economies. Austria (56.1), China (56), Singapore (56), and Japan (55.9) all score above the 55-point threshold, highlighting how these countries have significantly invested in their infrastructure to facilitate innovation and support economic growth. In the mid-range, countries like Kuwait (55.4), Belgium (54.6), Germany (54.5), and Switzerland (54.3) boast solid general infrastructure but may face specific challenges to maintain their level of innovation. Australia (53.7) and New Zealand (52.8) follow, demonstrating how geographical isolation can be mitigated by strong infrastructural investments. France (52.4) and the Netherlands (52) are other examples of advanced economies with well-developed infrastructure, while Mozambique surprises with a score of 51.5, indicating remarkable progress compared to other African countries. Countries like the Czech

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Republic (50.4) and Denmark (48.5) show how medium-sized European economies can excel in infrastructure. Lower in the rankings, countries like Brunei Darussalam (46.1), Spain (45.6), Saudi Arabia (44.7), and the UK (44.2) suggest that, despite their advanced economies, there are areas where infrastructure can be improved to better support innovation. Hong Kong SAR, China, with a score of 44.2, and Iran (43.3) reflect regional and political contexts that influence infrastructure. Israel (42.1), Ireland (42), Estonia (41.9), and Italy (41.9) indicate countries with good infrastructure that could benefit from further investments to better compete globally. Other European countries like Portugal (41.1), Hungary (40.6), and Croatia (33.6) show significant variations within the region. In the lower part of the rankings, countries like Uzbekistan (32.6), Serbia (32.2), Bulgaria (32.1), and South Africa (31.4) face significant challenges in general infrastructure. Greece (29.6), Nepal (29.6), and Latvia (29.3) reflect economies that, although having strengths, need infrastructural improvements to facilitate innovation. Countries like Mexico (28.8), Mongolia (28.7), Laos (28.5), and Malta (28.4) demonstrate the need for infrastructural investments to support economic growth and innovation. Lower still are Côte d'Ivoire (26.9), Argentina (26), and Brazil (26), representing emerging economies with great potential but significant infrastructural needs. At the bottom of the rankings, countries like Bangladesh (23.9), the Philippines (23.1), and Cameroon (22.9) show low scores indicating severe infrastructural deficiencies. Other countries like Uganda (21.4), Egypt (21), and Ghana (16.6) are in similar situations, facing significant challenges in improving their infrastructure to support innovation. Countries with the lowest scores, such as Angola (11.1), Iraq (8.9), and Zimbabwe (2.9), reflect contexts of economic or political crisis that heavily impact their infrastructure. Yemen, with the lowest score of 3.6, represents an extreme case of severely deficient infrastructure, often due to conflicts and political instability.

The Global General Infrastructure Index between 2013 and 2022. Analyzing the data related to the "General Infrastructure" indicator of the Global Innovation Index between 2013 and 2022 reveals notable variations both in absolute and percentage terms, revealing significant trends and changes in the infrastructure of various countries. Mozambique shows an impressive increase, rising from 20.9 to 51.5, with an absolute variation of 30.6 points and a percentage increase of 146.41%. This remarkable jump can be attributed to strategic investments in basic infrastructure, improvements in transportation and telecommunications, and greater political stability that allowed the development of sustainable infrastructure. Brunei Darussalam recorded substantial improvement, increasing from 24.6 to 46.1, with an absolute variation of 21.5 points and a percentage increase of 87.4%. This result reflects the country's efforts to diversify its economy beyond the energy sector by investing in transportation infrastructure and ICT to support innovation and economic development. Côte d'Ivoire improved its infrastructure from 16.2 to 26.9, with an absolute variation of 10.7 points and a percentage increase of 66.05%. This progress is likely the result of economic reforms and investments in critical infrastructure that facilitated economic growth and attracted foreign investments. Bahrain and Qatar recorded significant increases of 50.59% and 44.59%, with absolute variations of 21.6 and 23.5 points, respectively. Both countries focused their efforts on improving urban infrastructure, enhancing public services, and developing ICT to support their rapidly growing economies. Nepal saw a 43.69% increase, with an absolute variation of 9 points, reflecting investments in basic infrastructure and critical sectors like energy and telecommunications. Hungary and Ireland, with increases of 41.46% and 40.94% respectively, demonstrate how European economies are investing to improve their infrastructure to support innovation and global competitiveness. The Czech Republic, Germany, and Panama recorded increases of over 30%, with Germany showing an absolute variation of 13.2 points and a percentage increase of 31.96%. These countries have improved their

transportation and technological infrastructure, essential for maintaining high innovation capacity and economic development. Sweden, with an increase of 31.09% and an absolute variation of 16.2 points, continues to show strong investments in digital and sustainable infrastructure, maintaining its position as one of the most innovative countries in the world. Trinidad and Tobago, the Netherlands, and the UAE recorded significant improvements, with percentage increases of 30.69%, 30.33%, and 29.98%, respectively. Japan, Portugal, New Zealand, and Austria all showed significant increases in their infrastructure, demonstrating a continued commitment to improving infrastructural capacities to support innovation. Countries like Iran, Switzerland, and France showed moderate but significant increases, reflecting the importance of quality infrastructure for economic progress. Turkey, Denmark, and the UK, with increases of 24.2%, 24.04%, and 23.81%, show how European and Middle Eastern economies are improving their infrastructure to maintain competitiveness. Montenegro, Greece, and the Dominican Republic recorded increases of over 20%, reflecting significant progress in basic infrastructure. Other countries like Zambia, Slovenia, Singapore, and Italy showed modest but steady improvements, indicating a continued commitment to infrastructure improvement. However, countries like Slovakia, Malaysia, India, and Latvia recorded slight decreases in their infrastructure, highlighting possible economic and political challenges that negatively affected their progress. Bangladesh, Moldova, Mexico, Colombia, and Costa Rica showed moderate decreases, reflecting difficulties in maintaining and improving infrastructure in complex economic and political contexts. Brazil, Togo, Honduras, and Bulgaria recorded significant declines, suggesting structural problems hindering infrastructural progress. Some countries like Angola, El Salvador, Botswana, and Egypt recorded more pronounced decreases, with negative percentage variations exceeding 10%, indicating significant challenges in managing and developing infrastructure. Countries like Rwanda, Tanzania, Tajikistan, and Lithuania showed considerable declines, highlighting the need for strategic interventions to reverse these trends. Countries like Jamaica, Ghana, South Africa, and Mali recorded notable decreases, reflecting economic and political crises compromising their infrastructure. Argentina, Burkina Faso, Georgia, Jordan, and Uruguay showed significant decreases, suggesting difficulties in maintaining adequate infrastructure to support economic growth. Kenya, Senegal, Belarus, and Albania recorded marked declines, indicating structural problems hindering infrastructural progress. Peru, North Macedonia, Azerbaijan, and Sri Lanka showed notable decreases, highlighting the economic and political challenges negatively affecting infrastructural development. Ukraine, Luxembourg, Pakistan, Morocco, and Armenia recorded significant declines, reflecting crisis contexts that compromised their infrastructure. Guatemala, Mauritius, Mongolia, and Uganda showed notable decreases, suggesting severe economic and political challenges hindering infrastructural progress. Tunisia, Nicaragua, Namibia, Madagascar, Niger, Guinea, Yemen, and Zimbabwe all recorded drastic declines, with negative percentage variations exceeding 50% in some cases. These countries reflect the critical conditions of their infrastructure, often exacerbated by conflicts, political instability, and economic crises.

Economic Policies to Improve General Infrastructure. To improve general infrastructure, governments can adopt a range of targeted economic policies that span from direct public investments to creating a favorable environment for private investments. A fundamental strategy is to increase public investments in key infrastructural projects such as transportation, energy, water, and telecommunications. This can be financed through the issuance of infrastructure bonds, the use of public-private partnerships (PPP), and attracting foreign direct investments. PPPs, in particular, allow leveraging private sector expertise and resources while reducing the financial burden on the public sector. Another crucial aspect is reforming regulations and bureaucratic processes to make them more

streamlined and transparent. Simplifying authorization procedures and reducing bureaucracy can accelerate the implementation of infrastructural projects. Additionally, transparency and anti-corruption measures are essential to ensure that funds allocated to infrastructure are used efficiently and without waste. In this context, the adoption of digital technologies for project management and monitoring can improve transparency and efficiency. Diversifying funding sources is another important element. Besides public financing, governments can incentivize private investments through tax incentives, loan guarantees, and grants. Development banks, both national and international, can play a significant role by providing long-term and low-cost financing for infrastructural projects. Moreover, it is essential to create a stable and predictable regulatory framework that instills investor confidence and reduces risks associated with infrastructural investments. A particular focus should be on innovation and sustainability. Investing in green and sustainable infrastructure not only contributes to combating climate change but can also create new economic opportunities and jobs. Policies promoting the use of renewable energies, energy efficiency, and sustainable resource management are fundamental. Additionally, the adoption of advanced technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence, and smart city management systems can improve the efficiency and resilience of infrastructure. Finally, training and skill development are crucial. Investing in education and vocational training can ensure that the workforce is prepared to manage, maintain, and innovate infrastructure. Collaborations between governments, educational institutions, and the private sector can create training programs tailored to the specific needs of infrastructural projects.

Conclusions. Considering the global value of the General Infrastructure Index, we can see that on average this value grew by 3.67% between 2013 and 2022. Some countries saw their General Infrastructure Index value grow significantly above the period average, such as Mozambique with +146.41%, Brunei Darussalam with +87.40%, Côte d'Ivoire with +66.05%, Bahrain with +50.59%, Qatar with +44.59%, and Nepal with +43.69%. There are also countries where the General Infrastructure Index value significantly decreased between 2013 and 2022, such as Madagascar with -63.72%, Niger with -68.06%, Guinea with -69.57%, Yemen with -78.95%, and Zimbabwe with -87.61%.

Source: Global Innovation Index

Link: <https://prosperitydata360.worldbank.org/en/indicator/WIPO+GII+63>

Declarations

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